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Experiences from BiH: H2020 Twinning project SMARTWATER

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In January 2021, the new Horizon 2020 project “Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina” (SMARTWATER) was launched. It was the first time that an academic institution from Bosnia and Herzegovina implemented a Horizon 2020 project as Coordinator. The main objective of SMARTWATER is to reinforce networking, research and S&T cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), the University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other connected national institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and to increase their competency and fund-raising skills for a successful participation in the European Union Research Programs. Main project topics include: 1) cloud-based smart technologies, 2) new generation of satellite remote sensing data, 3) water-energy-food nexus and 4) climate change impact on agriculture. At two locations in BiH (Aleksandrovac and Butmir) 3-year field experiments on maize (*Zea mays* L.), hybrid BL 43 (from FAO 400 group) were completed. The Randomized Complete Block design included two factors, irrigation (3 irrigation regimes) and fertilization (2 nitrogen levels). During the project implementation, our scientific teams published several academic papers in peer-reviewed international Journals and Proceedings and these documents are available in open access on Zenodo platform [1]. The project consortium is preparing additional scientific papers. The project outputs are: 3 advanced training courses, 3 summer schools, joint research activities (experiments) at 2 locations in BiH, 3 stakeholders’ meetings (roundtables), 3 post-graduate MSc courses, 13 mutual staff exchanges, 3 hands-on workshops on R&I, the development of 2 smart water management tools and the organization of an international conference in BiH at the end of the project. So far (period 2021-2023) most of these activities were finished. All project reports were prepared and sent to the EC. All info about the project is being disseminated, on a regular basis, and for this purpose social media profiles were used: Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn and YouTube as well as the SMARTWATER website [2]. The dissemination of SMARTWATER achievements is an ongoing process. SMARTWATER project officially ends in June 2024. The remaining activities in 2024 include the organization of academic exchanges in Portugal and Italy, the 3rd stakeholders' meeting, the completion of the scientific publishing and the organization of an international conference in Trebinje (BiH) in May. We ask all interested stakeholders to visit our sites, to attend our events and to join the SMARTWATER network.

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REFERENCES

- [1] <https://zenodo.org/search?q=smartwater&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>
 [2] <https://www.smartwater-project.eu/>

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